

NAGRIKAL

CITIZENS VOICES
FOR AND FROM
SMALL CITIES

**AUGUST
2024**

RISE IN SEA LEVEL: FATE OF SMALL AND MID-SIZED COASTAL CITIES

CO₂

Part of Nagrikal Series -

Frontlines of climate change: Small and mid-sized Cities

A study on where small Indian cities stand in terms of climate change impacts and data availability

NAGRIKA

About Nagrika

Nagrika is a think-tank enabling citizens in small and mid-sized cities. We create knowledge that shapes unique, authentic and resilient cities. Through this knowledge, we mainstream the voice of citizens in decision making.

We co-create accessible and free knowledge resources for citizens and city governments. We have been creating knowledge about smaller cities from a small city. Much of this knowledge did not exist before and we strongly believe that what we are creating is needed by many but created by none. Our interventions have made it possible to understand these cities better. Slowly and steadily, our work has ensured that smaller cities become part of policy agendas of urban policy making.

We build a sense of ownership and community in small towns while strengthening city - policy - citizen relationship by demystifying public policy. Our activities include creating and amplifying voices from smaller cities, putting spotlight on developments in smaller cities, analyzing larger trends for their impact on smaller cities and various other initiatives that push the boundaries of thought and action in our small towns.

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This report is a living document and will be regularly updated. It is being informed by our ongoing research and co-created knowledge from various actors and institutions across multiple smaller cities.

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About the Series

This Nagrikal Series examines the relationship between climate change and cities, especially small and mid-sized cities*. It attempts to explore the dual roles of such cities- cities as contributors to and sufferers of climate change.

Through the series we contextualise some of the important impacts of climate change, like poor air quality, rising sea levels, rising temperatures, and increasing heatwaves with respect to smaller cities. The series highlights the limited share of knowledge on small cities, climate data availability, and monitoring. By bringing forth the facts and figures about smaller cities that are less talked about, we aim to enrich the discourse from our current understanding in an effort to build resilient small cities.

From defining the role of cities, especially the smaller cities, in climate change to exploring the share of such cities in research studies, climate data availability, and monitoring, the series aligns with our objective of creating knowledge for smaller cities to drive meaningful action.

We invite readers to engage with the findings of this report and join us in the collective effort to reimagine the future of small cities in the face of climate change. We believe that stakeholders at every level can make a significant change by utilising the insights provided in this publication. By understanding the city specific challenges, let us co-create innovative solutions to combat climate change impacts for a sustainable and resilient future.

We hope that this report will not just inform but also initiate a conversation about the challenges faced by small cities with regards to climate change in the policy discourse and climate action strategies, which is currently missing.

**Small and Mid-sized in this report refer to cities that have a population of up to 2.5 million.*

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List of Abbreviations

mm	Millimetre
ft	Feet
RMSI	Risk Management Solutions, Inc.
GIS	Geographic Information Systems
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
NASA	The National Aeronautics and Space Administration
SSP3-7.0	Shared Socioeconomic Pathways
NCCR	National Centre for Coastal Research
Km	Kilometre
INCOIS	Indian National Centre for Ocean Information Services
SOI	Survey of India
NIOT	National Institute of Ocean Technology
SAC	Space Applications Centre
ICZM	Integrated Coastal Zone Management
CRZ	Coastal Regulation Zone

Glossary

Accretion	Shifting of the shoreline towards the sea.
Annual Flood Level	Annual flood level is defined as the water level at the shoreline that local coastal floods exceed on average once per year.
Coastal Erosion	Erosion and shifting of shoreline towards the landmass.
Coastal Habitat	The natural environment found along coastlines, including beaches, estuaries, and wetlands.
Coastal Regulation Zone (CRZ)	Designated areas along the coast where construction and other activities are regulated to protect the environment and reduce damage from coastal hazards.
Cyclone	A large-scale air mass that rotates around a strong center of low atmospheric pressure, often leading to severe weather conditions. Rising sea surface temperatures and sea levels contribute to the increased intensity and frequency of cyclones.
Erosion Rate	The speed at which coastal land is worn away by natural forces such as waves, currents, and wind.
Groundwater and Soil Contamination	The process by which rising sea levels cause saltwater to intrude into freshwater aquifers and soils, leading to salination. This contamination can affect drinking water supplies and agricultural productivity in coastal areas.
Intense Cyclonic Storm	An extreme weather event driven by a combination of rising sea surface temperatures and a rise in sea level.
Melting Ice Sheets and Glaciers	The process by which ice sheets and glaciers lose mass due to rising temperatures, adding water to the oceans and contributing to sea level rise.

Salinity	The concentration of salts in seawater, which affects the density and movement of ocean currents.
Satellite altimeters	They measure sea level rise (changes in height relative to the centre of the planet) by measuring the return speed and intensity of radar.
Sea Level Projection Tool	A tool used to predict future sea level rise based on various climate scenarios and models.
Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs)	Scenarios used to project future climate change impacts based on different assumptions about societal, economic, and technological developments. SSP3-7.0 is a scenario where countries focus on local and regional interests, making it harder to address global climate change.
Thermal Expansion	The increase in the volume of seawater as it absorbs heat, contributing to sea level rise.
Tide Gauges	Mechanical systems, generally installed at ports, harbours, and other locations of strategic importance, that provide data essential for designing local coastal area plans.

Summary and Key Insights

Accelerated Sea Level Rise:

- a. Climate change, primarily driven by human activity, is accelerating the rise in sea levels globally. In December 2023, sea level was 104 mm above 1993's measure, which reveals the unprecedented rate at which the sea level is currently rising.
- b. This is the result of a two way effect. Sea level rise can be attributed to both the thermal expansion of seawater and melting of ice sheets and glaciers. In recent decades, the latter has become a more dominant contributor.

Impact on India's Smaller Coastal Cities:

- a. Sea level rise poses significant threats like erosion, flooding, and groundwater contamination in coastal cities worldwide, along with loss of vegetation and aquatic life. Several coastal cities in India, particularly smaller and mid-sized ones like Kochi and Visakhapatnam, face imminent risks of inundation and infrastructure damage.
- b. There are around 113 Indian cities spread across nine states that are at risk of getting submerged due to sea level rise by 2050. This report highlights that out of these, 109 are small and mid-sized coastal cities.
- c. Most of the vulnerable cities are located in Gujarat and Kerala, where coastal erosion is occurring at a high rate. In India, rural areas situated near the coastline are also at risk of getting submerged.

Increasing Extreme Weather Events:

- a. Rising sea levels contribute to the intensification of extreme weather events like cyclonic storms. This report points out how such events are occurring more frequently and with greater intensity, exacerbating the vulnerabilities of coastal communities.
- b. It is projected that, with the current trends, heating of the Indian Ocean is likely to increase four to eight times more by 2100. Therefore, category 4 or 5 storms may become relatively more common in the future for India's coastal cities.

Data Monitoring and Policy Responses:

- a. Collecting and maintaining sea level rise data is a complex process compared to monitoring air quality and temperature data. Continuous data availability for several decades is a necessity in this case.
- b. While tide gauges and satellite altimeters provide valuable data, there are challenges in terms of functionality and coverage. Furthermore, real time data on sea level is currently available only for 29 small and mid-sized cities.
- c. This report also highlights the knowledge gaps that exist in research regarding sea level rise, with the majority of it focusing on Mumbai.
- d. India has been implementing the Integrated Coastal Zone Management (ICZM) Plan to manage coastal areas through participatory initiatives at various organisational levels. However, this report highlights the need for studies at regional and local level, along with coastal regulations that cannot be easily compromised upon.

Rise in sea level: Fate of Small and Mid- sized coastal cities

Introduction

The rise in sea levels is another impact of climate change that is putting human life at risk and can create economic havoc in coastal cities. Oceans have already seen a record breaking increase in levels in 2022 and are expected to increase another three to four feet by the end of this century. Sea level rise is often associated with melting ice due to a warming climate; however, it is just one way that leads to the rise.

Coastal cities, especially in regions like the Indian Ocean, are at heightened risk due to faster-than-average sea level rise. For instance, cities in India such as Kochi, Visakhapatnam, and Thiruvananthapuram face significant threats, with projections indicating that hundreds of buildings could be affected by mid-century. The situation is exacerbated by the fact that the Indian Ocean is one of the fastest-warming oceans, contributing to thermal expansion. As sea levels continue to rise, the socio-economic and environmental challenges will intensify, necessitating robust policy responses and adaptive measures to protect vulnerable communities and ecosystems.

This article attempts to explore the reasons behind rising sea levels, their impact on cities, and what cities are doing and can do to combat this rise.

Climate Change and Its Dual Impacts on Local Climates and Sea Levels

The warming climate, as discussed in the first article, is changing the local climate or the local environment of the cities. It has an amplifying as well as a dampening effect on the natural conditions- like on the one hand, climate change is amplifying the extreme heat conditions, and on the other, it has a reducing effect on the amount of rainfall a particular area receives in normal conditions. The previous article discussed one of the amplifying effects- the rise in temperatures. Another amplifying effect that is threatening the cities- the coastal ones- is the rise in sea level.

Studies reveal that global sea levels have been rising at unprecedented rates that have never been seen in the previous 2,500+ years due to human caused global warming. It has already set a new record in 2022 of 101.2 mm rise above 1993 levels. As per the latest measurements in December 2023, this number has increased to 104 mm.

Climate change is accelerating the rise in sea levels in two ways. First, the rise in global temperatures increases the volume of the oceans as the sea water expands due to heat absorption (also known as thermal expansion). Second, the warming

climate melts the ice sheets and glaciers, which adds more water to the oceans. Until 2003, it was observed that melting ice and thermal expansion contributed equally to sea level rise. However, in recent decades, melting ice has contributed more. From 2005 to 2013, sea level rise due to melting ice was almost double the rise due to thermal expansion. As per the latest data from the World Glacier Monitoring Service, glaciers lost over 9,000 billion tons of ice from 1961-62 to 2015-16, raising sea levels by 27 mm.

Impact of Sea Level Rise

The rate of global sea level rise has shown a faster upward trend since 1900: 1.3 mm per year from 1901 to 1971, 1.9 mm per year from 1971 to 2006, and 3.7 mm per year from 2006 to 2018. The rate has further increased to 4.5 mm, that is, 0.015 ft per year, in the last decade (2013-2022).

Figure 1: The rate of global sea level rise has shown a faster upward trend since 1900

Source: Report- Global Sea-level Rise and Implications | WMO

Multiple studies suggest that the rapid increase since 1971 is mainly a result of human influence.

Sea level rise due to melting ice also induces climate change by altering the salinity of seawater. Salinity is directly linked to the movement of major ocean currents that help in heat transfer. The addition of fresh water to seawater decreases the salinity, which changes the seawater density. This leads to changes in the movement of ocean currents, which in turn alter heat transfer, causing climate change.

Sea level rise, however small it may be, has devastating impacts on the coastal habitat: it causes erosion (shifting of shoreline towards land), flooding, groundwater and soil contamination (due to salination), and loss of vegetation and aquatic life.

India's Coastal Cities at risk of getting submerged

Even though all the ocean basins are experiencing sea level rise, this rise is not uniform- some oceans have seen a rise of 150-200 mm since the beginning of the satellite records. Reports reveal that the rate of sea level rise in the south-western part of the Indian Ocean region is faster by 2.5 mm per year than the global average. The Indian Ocean is also one of the fastest warming oceans in the world, which is contributing to sea level rise due to thermal expansion.

The recent climate assessment report by the Ministry of Earth Sciences finds that the Indian Ocean rose at a rate of 1.75 mm per year between 1874 and 2004, which increased to 3.3 mm per year from 1993 to 2015. As a result, several coastal cities are at risk of getting submerged.

Increase in volume of sea water due to Thermal Expansion

Increase in volume of sea water due to melting of ice sheets & glaciers

Figure 2: The two way effect of Climate change on sea level rise
 Source: How is sea level rise related to climate change? | National Ocean Service

Figure 3: Small cities vulnerable to sea level rise in India
 Source: NASA's Sea Level Projection tool

A study by Risk Management Solutions Inc. (RMSI), a GIS consulting company, reveals that the average sea level rise by 2050 will have serious impacts on the population and infrastructure of several coastal cities in India, including the small and mid-sized cities like Kochi, Visakhapatnam, Mangalore, and Thiruvananthapuram. As per the analysis, sea level rise is likely to hit 464 buildings in Kochi, which can increase to 1,502 during high tide. Similarly, for Thiruvananthapuram, the expected number of buildings is 349, which may increase to 387 during high tide.

As per NASA's Sea Level Projection tool (which uses sea level projection data from the IPCC 6th Assessment Report), India has 12 coastal cities that are vulnerable to sea level rise. Out of the 12, nine are small and mid-sized cities, which include Kandla, Okha, Bhavnagar, Mormugao, Mangalore, Kochi, Paradip, Visakhapatnam, and Tuticorin. With the current rate of increase, these cities are vulnerable to a sea level rise of 1.77 to 2.7 feet by the end of the century.

The projections mentioned are based on a comparison with the average conditions between 1995 and 2014. They use a scenario called SSP3-7.0, which is part of a set of models called Shared Socioeconomic Pathways. These models help us think about what might happen in the future by considering how society, the economy, politics, and technology might change and how these changes could impact our climate goals for the year 2100.

Specifically, SSP3-7.0 is a scenario where countries focus more on local and regional interests rather than working together on global issues, which makes it harder to deal with climate change.

State wise distribution of sinking cities in India

There are around 113 cities (taken from Climate Central's tool) spread across nine states that are at risk of getting submerged due to sea level rise by 2050. Out of these, 109 are small and mid-sized coastal cities. Most of these cities are spread across two states: Gujarat and Kerala, whereas Goa has the fewest. Apart from small and mid-sized urban areas, many of the rural areas located near the coastline are also at risk of getting submerged in these states.

Out of the total 109 small and mid-sized cities, 21 are located in Gujarat. The state has a 1945.60 km long coastline- the longest in the country. However, it is

West Bengal's coastline is eroding at the fastest rate compared to other coastal states!

Figure 4: Erosion rate of coastal States

Source: Assessment report by the National Centre for Coastal Research

shrinking due to climate change as sea levels are rising. As per the assessment report titled National Assessment of Shoreline Changes Along Indian Coast by the National Centre for Coastal Research (NCCR), the state's coastline is eroding at a rate of 27.6% due to sea level rise. Until 2016, the shoreline was eroding at a rate of 26.3%, but between 2016 and 2018, erosion took away more than 25 km of land. As a result, along with the bigger coastal cities like Surat, many of the small and mid-sized cities in the state are at the risk of getting submerged due to rising sea levels.

Kerala also has 21 vulnerable small and mid-sized coastal cities. The state is home to the city that is set to face the second highest sea level rise by 2100 among small and mid-sized cities- Kochi. The state's 592.96 km long coastline is eroding at a rate of 46.4% due to sea level rise, which is over 1.5 times the rate for Gujarat's coastline. As per the latest study by the University of Kerala, the highest erosion rate of 35 feet (10.59 m) per year has been observed at Pozhiyoor. This means that land almost equal to the width of a doubles tennis court gets eroded (or submerged) every year along the Pozhiyoor coast. The study further finds that the state has already lost around 2.62 square kilometers of land to the sea along Thiruvanthapuram's coast in the period 2006-2020, indicating that the beaches in the district might vanish in the next five years if no action is taken to prevent further loss.

Associated extreme weather events

An intense cyclonic storm is an extreme weather event driven by a combination of rising sea surface temperatures and a rise in sea level. Cyclones have been intensifying at a faster pace in recent years. The number of days in which low

pressure winds intensified into a cyclonic storm has decreased from 2-3 days to just 1 day. The same was observed in Gujarat's cyclonic storm, Biparjoy. The low pressure area in the Arabian Sea on June 5, 2023, quickly developed into a Depression on June 6, which then intensified into a cyclone storm on June 7. The low pressure winds turned into a Very Severe Cyclonic Storm three days before the IMD forecast had originally suggested. Similar was the case with cyclone Michaung which was identified as a low pressure area on November 29 and developed into a cyclonic storm by December 3. The cyclone induced heavy rain in the city of Chennai and other districts of Tamil Nadu, which led to flooding, leaving several people stranded. Most recently, cyclone Remal, which impacted eastern India and Bangladesh in late May 2024, was also caused by a similar combination of atmospheric and oceanic conditions brought forth by climate change.

Biparjoy's track

Biparjoy's impact

Biparjoy became **the longest lived cyclone- took 10 days to make landfall** in Gujarat.

Source : IMD; The New Indian Express

An increase in sea level means an increase in the volume of the sea, which in turn means a rise in ocean heat content through heat absorption. It is reported that about 92% of the radiated heat goes into the ocean. The increased pace of cyclonic storms is a result of the increased heat content and higher sea surface temperatures. The fastest sea surface warming has occurred in the Indian Ocean. The ocean's heat content has increased from 1971 to 2018 by 0.396 joules and is likely to increase four to eight times more by 2100 under the 'business-as-usual' scenario. This means that category 4 or 5 storms may become relatively more common in the future.

A report by the Ministry of Earth Sciences reveals that there has been a 49% increase in severe cyclonic storms in the Bay of Bengal region and a 52% increase in the Arabian Sea region annually in the post-1950 era of global warming.

Share of small and mid-sized cities in Data Monitoring

Changes in sea level are mapped in two major ways: tide gauges and satellite altimeters. Tide gauges measure sea level rise relative to the height of land by monitoring daily low and high tides. In India, there are two main platforms to look for sea level data: Indian National Centre for Ocean Information Services (INCOIS) and the Survey of India (SOI).

A real time network of tide gauges has been established by SOI and the National Institute of Ocean Technology (NIOT) as part of the Indian Tsunami Early Warning System. It comprises 50 state-of-the-art tide gauges (36 by SOI and 14 by NIOT) transmitting real time data through satellite communication to INCOIS at

Hyderabad, SOI at Dehradun, and NIOT at Chennai for processing and interpretation. Out of the total 36 tide gauges that are being used to monitor real time data under the Indian Tsunami Early Warning System, 32 are located in small and mid-sized cities.

Figure 5: Location of Indian Tsunami Early Warning System in 32 small and mid-sized cities

Source: Indian National Centre for Ocean Information Services

Tide gauges are generally installed at ports, harbours, and other locations that are strategically important. Tide gauges are mechanical systems that provide reliable data and are essential for designing local coastal area plans. However, their non functionality poses a challenge for continuous data collection. Continued functionality of tide gauges is essential, as to determine the sea level rise that has been caused by climate change, researchers need continuous data or measurements for several decades—ideally more than 50 to 60 years. Currently, out of the 36 tide gauges, 3 are non functional. The only tide gauge that has been recording sea level data

continuously for more than 100 years is located in Mumbai.

Satellite altimeters measure sea level rise (changes in height relative to the centre of the planet) by measuring the return speed and intensity of radar; the higher the sea level, the faster and stronger the return signal. In contrast to tide gauges, which monitor the sea level every day, satellite altimeters monitor the sea level at a particular place once every 10 days. However, due to its continuous data collection, the satellite altimeters have been instrumental in figuring out the possible causes of sea level rise, i.e., whether the rise is an outcome of climate change or not. This is difficult with tide gauge data as it measures the sea level relative to land, which is also dynamic in nature. Bad weather (cloud cover and rainfall) and altimeter track loss may hinder monitoring through satellite.

Share of small and mid-sized cities in Data Availability

The Space Applications Centre (SAC), in collaboration with the Central Water Commission, maps the shoreline changes using satellite data. The agency has created a Shoreline Change Atlas for each of the coastal states of India for 2004-2006 and 2014-16 time frames. While the Atlas acts as an inventory for shoreline changes and covers information on coastal erosion (shoreline shifts landwards) and accretion (shoreline shifts seawards), it doesn't give the shoreline change in kilometers at city level in each state. For example, the atlas for Gujarat states that the state has gained about 208 hectares of land due to accretion but lost 313 hectares of land due to erosion. Such numbers are not available at the city level for the state.

The real time data on sea level is currently available for only 29 small and mid-sized cities. The tide gauges in the remaining 3 cities are not reporting, hence the data is unavailable. Out of the two big cities on the list, Kolkata and Chennai, data is available only for Garden Reach port in Kolkata.

The Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level, a global data bank for long term sea level change information based at the National Oceanography Centre in UK, covers 24 Indian cities. Out of these 24, only 3 are big cities. The most recent data, that is, the data for 2023, is available only for 11 small and mid-sized cities.

Share of small and mid-sized cities in Research studies

We have reviewed 30 journal articles (both national and international) published between 2013 and 2022 with some reference to the rise in sea levels, shoreline changes, and coastal flooding to analyse the availability of knowledge on sea level rise in small and mid-sized cities. It is observed that about 36% of these studies focus on the bigger cities like Mumbai, Kolkata, Surat, and Chennai. Similarly, around 36% focus on small and mid-sized cities like Kochi, Cuddalore, Thiruvananthapuram, and Visakhapatnam. Around 27% of the studies focused on small and mid-sized, as well as, big cities. It is interesting to note that 40% of the studies mentioned the rising sea levels in Mumbai, indicating the prime focus on the city in the research landscape of this area.

Of the 30 studies reviewed, studies focused on sea level assessment along Indian coastal areas and the impact of sea level rise had the same share of 33%.

About 13% focus on calculating the coastal vulnerability index for urban areas, while 10% study urban flooding risks associated with sea level rise. Of the 30 studies, 2 focus on sea level rise due to land subsidence, while only 1 focuses on local perceptions of climate change and sea-level rise.

Policy response to Sea Level rise in India

India has been implementing the Integrated Coastal Zone Management (ICZM) Plan in collaboration with the World Bank to manage the coastal areas in the country. There are four components being implemented under the project: the National Coastal Management Programme, ICZM-West Bengal, ICZM-Orissa, and ICZM-Gujarat. The National Coastal Management Programme includes the mapping and demarcation of hazard lines along the coastal line. Under this programme, Coastal Regulation Zone rules (CRZ) are being implemented to limit construction activities in coastal areas and reduce damage due to coastal flooding and high intensity cyclones.

As per the CRZ notification 2018, the land between the low tide line and the high tide line, plus the coastal areas of creeks, bays, rivers, and backwaters that are subject to tides up to 500 metres from the high tide line, are designated as coastal regulatory zones. These are further classified into four types: CRZ I, CRZ II, CRZ III, and CRZ IV. However, these rules are easily tweaked in the name of development. For example, CRZ norms were tweaked in 2015 to allow construction of Chhatrapati Shivaji's Statue on Mumbai's coast. In March 2023, the Goa government tweaked its coastal plan to allow fishermen to carry out commercial and tourism activities in CRZ areas.

ICZM-West Bengal, ICZM-Orissa, and ICZM-

Figure 6: Share of Small cities as compared to Big cities

Source : INCOIS & Research studies

Gujarat are the state specific plans for their coastal area management. For example, under ICZM-Orissa the state has identified two coastal stretches, Gopalpur to Chilika and Paradip to Dhamra, to establish sustainable levels of economic and social activity in these stretches and build infrastructure that is resilient to storm surges and flooding.

ICZM calls for participatory management of coastal zones and therefore focuses on the integration of different sectors related to the coastal areas and achieving coherence among public and private initiatives and all decisions by the authorities at all three levels: the national, regional, and local.

Conclusion

The rise in sea levels, driven by climate change, poses a significant threat to coastal cities, particularly small and mid-sized ones. This phenomenon threatens these urban areas with erosion, flooding, and a host of socio-economic challenges. Indian coastal cities, facing accelerated sea level rises, exemplify the urgent need for tailored adaptation strategies to safeguard infrastructure, populations, and ecosystems.

The three bigger coastal cities, that is, Mumbai, Chennai, and Kolkata, have always been in the limelight for the rise in sea level along their coasts; however, a larger share of small and mid-sized cities are also at a higher risk of getting submerged. For instance, Okha, Bhavnagar, Mormugao, Kochi, and Paradip can face a higher rise in sea levels by 2100 as compared to Mumbai and Chennai. The rise that Bhavnagar can face is almost 1.5 times that of Mumbai. Statewise, Gujarat and Kerala coastlines have faced the highest erosion due to sea level rise. Therefore, all the small and mid-sized urban centres in these two states are equally vulnerable to rising sea levels.

The rise in sea level seems to be the only impact, which is a result of the two way effect of a warming climate. The melting of ice sheets is a visible cause of rising sea levels; however, thermal expansion, which expands oceans in terms of volume, is also

significant despite being an invisible cause. The rise has set new records in recent years, and studies indicate that the melting of ice sheets has become the dominant cause behind this rise. Like the previous two impacts of climate change, sea level rise and climate change are also interdependent- climate change induces sea level rise, sea level rise induces climate change.

Collecting and maintaining sea level rise data is a complex process compared to monitoring air quality and temperature data. To analyse the rise in sea level due to climate change, continuous data availability for several years is a necessity, which is not possible through tide gauges as not all the gauges have been functional all the time in the past. The only tide gauge that has been monitoring sea level for more than a century is located in Mumbai. Similarly, cloud cover can influence the data collected by the satellite altimeters. Knowledge gaps exist not only in terms of data monitoring but also in the research landscape. Majority of the research studies analysed in this study are focused on the sea level rise in Mumbai.

The policy response to sea level rise in India is largely focused on building infrastructure that is resistant to flooding and intense cyclonic storms. However, these construction norms under CRZ rules are easily tweaked as per need. India lacks a regional assessment that can help identify the areas that are most vulnerable and at high risk due to rising sea levels. Predictions by global models like the IPCC under various scenarios are helpful in determining the rate at which the rise will occur. But in order to identify the nature and extent of inundation and plan for area specific responses, studies at the regional and local level are essential.

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Bhavnagar: The small city at the highest risk

Bhavnagar, a small city in the Saurashtra region of Gujarat, is set to witness a sea level rise of up to 2.7 feet (0.82 m) by 2100 under the SSP3-7.0 scenario. This is the highest sea level rise among the small and mid-sized coastal cities and the second highest among all the 12 vulnerable coastal cities in the country. Interestingly, the projected rise in global mean sea level by the end of the century is 2.2 feet (0.68 m)- around 1.2 times less than the projected rise in Bhavnagar.

Bhavnagar is projected to be underwater by the end of the century if the sea level continues to rise at its current trajectory.

However, the small city faces deficiencies in terms of knowledge creation, monitoring networks, and current data availability. For example, none of the 30 research studies published between 2013 and 2022 focused on Bhavnagar. The majority of the studies discuss the rising sea levels in Mumbai. Similarly, Bhavnagar is missing in the tide gauge system set up under the Indian Tsunami Early Warning System. The Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level does include Bhavnagar but the sea level

"Annual flood level" is defined as the water level at the shoreline that local coastal floods exceed on average once per year.

Figure 7: Bhavnagar- Land below Annual flood level for the year 2050 and 2100

Source: Climate Central's Coastal Risk Screening tool

According to Climate Central's Coastal Risk Screening tool, the coastal city can face a water level of around 3 to 4 meters above the high tide line by 2100, which could be reached through combinations of sea level rise, tides, and storm surge. This

data available for the city is from the year 1980. Even the ICZM-Gujarat focuses on the Gulf of Kutch area, leaving out Bhavnagar, which lies near the Gulf of Khambhat, also known as the Gulf of Cambay.

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Important Reads

NASA Sea Level
Projection tool

<https://sealevel.nasa.gov/ipcc-ar6-sea-level-projection-tool>

Climate Central Coastal
Risk Screening tool

<https://coastal.climatecentral.org/>

National Centre for
Coastal Research
Technical Reports

<https://www.nccr.gov.in/?q=technical-report>

INCOIS Tide Gauge
Network

<https://tsunami.incois.gov.in/TEWS/Link.do?function=tgStationList>

Integrated Coastal Zone
Management

<https://www.basu.org.in/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/integrated-coastal-zone-managment.pdf>

